

DYSKINETIC CEREBRAL PALSY: NEW APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION

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Abstract. *Cerebral palsy refers to a group of non-progressive diseases characterized by impaired volitional movements or posture and resulting from prenatal malformations or perinatal or postnatal damage to the central nervous system [1]. Cerebral palsy manifests itself before the age of 2 years [1]. The exact cause of CP is unknown, but scientists identify a number of factors that can be triggers for this pathology, such as nuclear jaundice, prematurity, intrauterine disorders, neonatal encephalopathy. The following types of CP are distinguished: spastic, athetoid, ataxic and mixed. Athetoid cerebral palsy, also known as dyskinetic cerebral palsy, is the second most common subtype of cerebral palsy [2]. It is a non-progressive, permanent disorder that results from a stroke in the brain of the fetus or infant [2]. This type of cerebral palsy is manifested by bradykinetic, involuntary movements of the trunk and limbs in the proximal parts, which become more frequent with excitement or with voluntary movement. Sometimes jerky (choroid) movements can be observed.*

Keywords: cerebral palsy, athetoid type, involuntary movements, choreoid movements.

Relevance. At the moment, there is a limitation of data on the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of the athetoid form of cerebral palsy. The diagnosis of this pathology is made on the basis of clinical data. There is a shortage of new imaging and laboratory methods for diagnosing cerebral palsy. Treatment is based on rehabilitation measures, spasm relief and orthopedic surgery. There is a need to find new methods for treating cerebral palsy. Patients with dyskinetic cerebral palsy have a higher rate of early death than with other subtypes of cerebral palsy due to an increased number of complications and disabilities compared to them. [3] Since this pathology leads to respiratory failure, the causes of which are pneumonia and aspiration, due to swallowing disorders.

Objective. To consider new methods for diagnosing, treating and preventing the dyskinetic form of cerebral palsy by analyzing modern studies conducted around the world.

Tasks.

1. To analyze theoretical ideas about the dyskinetic form of cerebral palsy.
2. To analyze data on new methods of diagnostics, treatment and prevention of dyskinetic cerebral palsy.

Materials and methods. Theoretical research methods: analysis, synthesis, generalization, deduction. Literary and Internet data on new methods of diagnostics, treatment and prevention of cerebral palsy were analyzed and studied.

Results.

The main diagnostic methods for all forms of cerebral palsy are a thorough history of asphyxia during childbirth, jaundice, meningitis, seizures, neonatal stroke, muscle hypotonia or hypertonia. Another method for diagnosing the dyskinetic form of cerebral palsy is the use of clinical scales to measure the severity of dystonia and choreoathetosis, these include the Barry-

Albright Dystonia Rating Scale, the Burke-Fahn-Marsden Dystonia Rating Scale (BFMS) and the Dyskinesia Disorders Scale. But they have their limitations, due to the difficulty of measuring choreoathetosis. Using visualization methods such as ultrasound, it is possible to determine the presence of periventricular changes in the brain matter. But all of the above diagnostic methods are not accurate, but only suggest this pathology.

- Spastic diplegia
- Spastic quadriplegia
- Dyskinetic
- Ataxic
- Hemiplegic
- Mixed

Different types of cerebral palsy [4]

In addition to the above methods, this diagnosis can be made on the basis of MRI of the brain. Seventy percent of patients with dyskinetic cerebral palsy have lesions detected on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain in the basal ganglia or thalamus. In a few patients, the scans appear normal.[5][6] Other lesions may be detected. Patients with kernicterus commonly have lesions in the globus pallidus.[7]

Basal ganglia damage in dyskinetic cerebral palsy [8].

A 2016 study from the Children's Neurological Hospital in Boston, Massachusetts, conducted a high-quality systematic review of basal ganglia and thalamic lesions in dyskinetic cerebral palsy. Studies examining the lentiform nuclei showed that all subjects (19 of 19) had lesions in the lentiform nuclei. Studies examining the putamen and globus pallidus also showed that all subjects (35 of 35) had lesions in the lentiform nuclei (i.e., lesions in the putamen or globus pallidus); isolated lesions in the subthalamic nucleus, thalamus, and putamen caudate were also found. As a result, two types of dyskinetic cerebral palsy were identified, depending on the involvement of the lentiform nucleus: with predominant damage to the putamen and with panlenticular damage affecting the putamen and the globus pallidus. The reason for dividing into groups is the prognosis of the effectiveness of such a treatment method as deep brain stimulation. Treatment of the dyskinetic type of cerebral palsy can only be symptomatic, since this pathology has no established cause. This treatment is aimed at eliminating symptoms such as dystonia and choreoathetosis, as well as concomitant diseases: depression and epilepsy. Drugs such as oral baclofen, a GABA-B agonist, trihexyphenidyl are often used in the treatment of dyskinetic cerebral palsy; however, most of them show low efficiency [9]. If oral forms of baclofen are ineffective, an intrathecal form of drug administration is sometimes used, which has shown a reduction in side effects and greater efficiency in relieving the symptoms of dystonia.

The newest treatment for the drug-resistant form of dyskinetic CP is Deep Brain Stimulation. It is used to reduce dystonia, but the benefits in terms of quality of life and functionality are less than in patients with primary (hereditary) dystonia [10]. In 2013, a comparative study of 17 children aged 7 to 15 years with primary dystonia and CP was conducted in the United States after deep brain stimulation. While patients with cerebral palsy had significantly more motor disability than the DYT1 cohort at baseline, both groups demonstrated improvement after 1 year (cerebral palsy = 24%; DYT1 = 6%)[11].

Botulinum toxin is another treatment used to treat dystonia in CP. There is some evidence that it reduces pain and dystonia in patients with CP [12]. The main areas of cerebral palsy prevention are the prevention of risk factors in pregnant women and newborns: prematurity, low birth weight, preeclampsia in women in labor. Early detection and diagnosis of the dyskinetic form of cerebral palsy can lead to early referral of patients to appropriate specialists, which will improve the prognosis for the effectiveness of treatment, as well as reduce the risk of complications.

Conclusion. This article discusses the main and new methods of diagnosis, treatment and prevention of the dyskinetic type of cerebral palsy. Given the high risk of complications in such patients and the similarity of clinical and instrumental signs, it was necessary to conduct differential diagnostics with movement disorders, neuromuscular disorders, neurodegenerative disorders and congenital metabolic disorders.

In the past few years, thanks to numerous studies and technological developments, a number of promising visualization and laboratory markers have been identified for the comprehensive diagnosis of the dyskinetic form of cerebral palsy, including at the initial stages of the neurodegenerative process. Treatment methods such as cord blood therapy, nanomedicine and stem cell therapy need to be studied in more detail in the future for application in clinical practice [13].

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